

Preventive Measures for Fault Conditions of a 500kV Insulator

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Abstract: In this research, the fault condition of the composite insulator of a 500kV line linear tower is analyzed. The reason behind the fault was obtained and correspondingly preventive measures are put forward that must be taken. The case study taken was the chemical composition and operating conditions of the insulator silicone rubber sheath. It was concluded that under the combined action of sheath damage, poor sealing, yearly aging, as well as under the repeated action of the corona, nitric acid, OH and COOH concentration, there might be penetrating cracks and holes in the sleeve, making the insulator mandrel in direct contact with the outside air, rainwater, etc. Using macro inspection, anatomical inspection, micro observation and dye penetration test, infrared temperature measurement test and electric field simulation calculation are carried out on the normal phase insulator of the same tower, and the chemical composition of the insulator core rod is analyzed, and it is concluded that the fault phase insulator sheath has its own defects, poor sealing and other problems, causing the mandrel to come into contact with the outside air, rainwater, etc., and the mandrel will be corroded under the long-term action of the strong electric field, acid solution and humid air resulting in the insulator disconnection.

Key words: *mandrel, linear tower, epoxy resin, fiberglass, silicone rubber sheath, composite insulator*

1. Introduction

In general, a composite insulator consists of three parts: metal ends, silicone rubber sheaths, and epoxy resin-impregnated glass fiber mandrels. The glass fibers in the mandrel mainly carries mechanical loads. Composite insulators have been widely used in high-voltage transmission lines due to their good pollution flashover resistance, light weight and convenient operation and maintenance [1-3].

However, with the increased use of composite insulators, the probability of accidents is also increasing. According to literature statistics and analysis, the on-site damage of composite insulators basically includes mechanical damage (including mandrel breakage or shed damage) [4-6] and electrical damage (lightning flashover or bond

interface breakdown) [7-8]. The fracture of the mandrel can cause the insulator to break the string. This kind of accident has serious consequences, which will lead to the tripping accident of the single suspension string linear tower, which has a serious impact on the safe operation of the power grid. In this paper, the reasons for the disconnection of the composite insulator of the linear tower of a 500kV line are studied and analyzed, and preventive measures are proposed.

2. 500kV Linear Tower Composite Insulator Broken String Overview

On December 3, 2018, the working staff inspected line faults and found that the middle phase (B phase) composite insulator of the #72 tower was broken, and the middle phase conductor fell to the ground.

As shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The tower type #72 is SZT42-33, the tower insulator is designed with a single I-string, the model is FXBW-500/210, the rated mechanical load is 210kN, the structure height is 4360mm, and the hanging time is May 26, 2006, and the production time is March 2005.

Fig.1 Middle-phase insulator fracture

Fig. 2 The wire has fallen to the ground

2.1 Visual inspection of composite insulators with broken strings

Broken string insulators had a total of 84 sheds and the fracture is located between the 5th to 6th sheds at the high voltage end. The fracture surface of the mandrel at the fracture is not neat like the tip of a brush, the root is powdered, and the surface is carbonized black. There is one crack and one perforation at the fracture, and the sheath at the fracture is severely powdered. From the 1st shed on the high-voltage end to the 15th shed, there are cracks and perforations in the sheath under the shed, a total of 18 cracks and 17

perforations, and no perforations and cracks were found above the 15th shed. The details are shown in Figure 3-6.

Figure 3 Fracture and mandrel at the fracture

Figure 4 Umbrella cover powder

Figure 5 Jacket crack

Figure 6 Sheath Perforation

2.2 Anatomical inspection of composite insulators with broken strings

The insulator was dissected along the high-voltage end to the low-voltage end as shown in figure 7 and it was found that the length of the deterioration channel was about 2.3 meters. Part of the fiberglass color turns black and part turns reddish brown. The interface between the sheath and the mandrel is loosely bonded, and the sheath becomes brittle and hardened.

Fig. 7 The mandrel appears pulverized and carbonized

3. Infrared temperature measurement test

Infrared temperature measurement test was carried out on the A-phase and C-phase insulators of a 500kV line, first a voltage of 500kV for 30min was applied and as a result, the voltage dropped down to the highest operating phase voltage of 318kV, the temperature of the insulator remained stable for 30min. The ambient temperature of the test was 7°C

and the humidity was 40%. According to the field test results, there is no abnormal temperature rise in the A-phase and C-phase insulators of a 500kV line. As shown in Figures 8 and 9.

Fig-8 Test diagram of insulator with applied voltage

Fig-9 Insulator infrared temperature measurement test diagram

3.1 Electric field simulation calculation

A model for calculating the electric field of the insulator was established based on the size drawing of the equalizing ring. The dielectric constant values of 3.5 and 5 were assigned to the silicon rubber and mandrel, respectively. The ball head was subjected to the peak operating voltage while the ball socket was grounded, and the solution domain was considered infinite. The overall potential and field strength distribution of the insulator were examined using the established model, and it was found that there were no notable abnormalities, as depicted in figure 10.

Fig-10 Electric field calculation diagram

3.2 Dye penetration

To conduct this testing, three samples were collected for each insulator of the #72 tower's A, B, and C phases. These samples were processed to meet the necessary size and style requirements for the test. A test container tray was prepared with a layer of glass balls of uniform diameter, into which a 1% violet methylene dye in ethanol staining solution was poured. After 15 minutes, the samples were observed to determine the penetration of the dye. The results indicated that neither phase A nor phase C showed any signs of dye penetration, indicating that they met the standard requirements. However, the B-phase sample showed dye penetration throughout the sample along the interface between the mandrel and the sheath, indicating that it did not meet the standard requirements. The results of the dye testing showed that the interface between the faulty insulator mandrel and the sheath had failed, and the sealing was not tight.

3.3 Microscopic observation

To examine the fractured mandrel, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to observe its microscopic morphology, and an energy dispersive analyzer (EDS) attached to the SEM was used to analyze the elemental composition of the micro-area sample. Low and high magnification images of the fracture are presented in Figures 11 and 12. As shown in Figure 11, the glass fibers have become detached from the epoxy matrix, leaving the fibers fully exposed. The glass fibers were significantly

damaged and broken, with numerous fragments adhering to the surface of the broken glass fibers. Figure 12 provides a more detailed magnification of the broken glass fiber and the concentrated area of debris. It reveals that the surface of the broken fiber is densely covered with protrusions and particles.

Fig-11 Microscopic appearance of fracture initiation position at low magnification

Fig-12 Microscopic appearance of fracture initiation position at high magnification

Upon conducting trace element EDS analysis of the glass fibers and surface fragments, it was found that the primary elements present in the fragments and glass fibers were O, Si, Ca, Al, and small amounts of Na and Mg. However, no C element was observed. This indicates that the epoxy resin matrix has been entirely decomposed in the cracking corrosion area of the mandrel, and the fragments consist mostly of scattered glass fibers. Analysis of the solid part of the mandrel using SEM microscopic morphology and Energy-Dispersive X-

ray Spectroscopy (EDS) element analysis revealed that the glass fiber was severely damaged by electrical corrosion, resulting in fractures and an uneven surface. Another observation was that the mandrel had cracked, and the epoxy resin matrix was decomposed under the influence of the electric field and moisture, leading to the glass fiber losing its protective coating.

4. Analysis of the causes of broken strings of synthetic insulators

4.1 Analysis of sheath perforation and crack

The insulator sheath of the composite insulator is composed of silicone rubber material, which mainly consists of polydimethylsiloxane ($[(CH_3)_2SiO]_n$) and includes a proportion of carbon black and $Al(OH)_3$ filler [9]. Upon examining the faulty insulator (B phase) and the non-faulty insulators (A, C phase) of the same tower, it was observed that the sheath of the faulty insulator had penetrating cracks and perforations between the sheds, while the non-faulty items did not have such defects. Eighteen synthetic insulator sheaths from six-base iron towers on the same line were inspected, and no penetrating cracks or perforations were found. The faulty phase composite insulator was found to have sheath damage defects during production, handling, and installation, along with issues of bonding failure at the interface between the mandrel and the sheath, and poor sealing quality.

In wet environments, the interface between the mandrel and the sheath in composite insulators with defects can quickly allow moisture to penetrate and fill the entire interface [10]. As a result, the electric field on the inner surface of the sheath at the radial cross-section of the air gap is much higher than the electric field on the outer surface. This creates wear that results in cracks and holes, generating ozone. In addition, during corona discharge, high-energy electron beams act on water molecules in the air, generating free $-OH$ that then combines with the chemical bond on the surface of the silicone rubber

material to produce $-COOH$ and associative $-OH$. Under high humidity conditions, there are more water molecules in the air, resulting in the generation of more associative OH and $COOH$ during the aging process, which further increases the aging degree [12]. Over time, surface cracks and holes gradually appear [13].

While normal phase insulators may also face aging problems during extended operation, the faulty phase insulators are more susceptible to aging issues due to bonding failure at the interface between the mandrel and the sheath, poor sealing quality, and repeated exposure to corona, nitric acid, $-OH$, and $-COOH$. These factors, combined with sheath damage and poor sealing, can result in penetrating cracks and holes in the sheath.

4.2 Analysis of Causes of Disconnection

The mandrel in a composite insulator can experience problems such as sheath perforation and cracks, which can lead to direct contact with external media such as air and rainwater. This can result in the formation of a black carbonized channel along the white hydrolysis channel on the surface of the mandrel under the influence of the electric field. As time passes, the carbonized channel can rapidly develop in the direction of the electric field, leading to the failure of the interface between the glass fiber and the epoxy resin in the carbonization channel. This causes the glass fiber to become loosely arranged, and a large number of damaged epoxy resin matrix remains around the glass fiber.

When the carbonization channel of the mandrel rod becomes long enough, it can cause a difference in the gradient of the inner and outer potentials of the composite insulator sheath. This can cause the sheath to break down and form a sheath damage hole, forcing the inner and outer potentials of the sheath to be consistent. Partial discharge at the interface can continue, and when the carbonization channel becomes long enough, the sheath can break down again and form a sheath damage hole. This process can repeat, resulting in the formation of multiple punch holes on the composite insulator sheath and an

increase in the number of cracks. The formation of carbonized channels is therefore an important factor in the penetration of cracks and perforations in insulators. Cracks and holes are often concentrated at the high-voltage end of the insulator due to the strong electric field strength.

During long-term operation, the mandrel can come into contact with external media such as air and moisture, causing moisture to diffuse from the outside to the inside of the mandrel. This can lead to swelling, hydrolysis, and plasticization of the mandrel epoxy resin matrix. Larger wet mismatch stress can cause interface de-bonding, cracking, and other phenomena. Periodic moisture absorption and dehumidification processes can cause matrix fatigue, generating micro-cracks and micro-holes in the matrix and interface. When defects such as micro-cracks, micro-holes, or interface de-bonding and cracking occur inside the mandrel, it can further promote the intrusion of moisture and increase the amount of moisture.

There is nitrogen in the air, and elements such as silicic acid and sulfur exist in the synthetic insulator. Under the influence of a strong electric field and moisture, they can electrochemically react to form an acid solution. Under long-term exposure to the acid solution, strong electric field, and humid air, the alkali oxides contained in the mandrel glass fiber can chemically react with the acid solution and other substances. The glass fiber will gradually break down as a result of the electrochemical reaction. When the fracture surface becomes significant, and the total bearing capacity of the unbroken glass fiber cannot withstand the comprehensive load force, such as the dead weight of the wire and the vibration of the wire, the mandrel can be pulled off as a whole, resulting in the insulator breaking. The fracture surface is irregular, and the fractured end resembles the tip of a brush, indicating that the mandrel is not brittle, but rather a rotten fracture.

5. Precautions

There is a need to strengthen the infrared detection of composite insulators, if local overheating is found, replace them in time, carry out the double-string transformation of composite insulators for transmission lines, strengthen the whole process management of composite insulators in transportation, construction, acceptance, maintenance and other links, especially not to damage the mandrel sheath, prevent the insulator sheath from being pecked by birds and strictly control the production process of composite insulators to ensure qualified quality.

6. Conclusion

The main focus of this research is to analyze the circumstances of poor sealing of a faulty phase insulator After aging year by year and under the repeated action of the corona, nitric acid, OH and COOH, the sheath has penetrating cracks and holes as a result, the core rod carbonization channel is formed. The difference between the inner and outer potentials of the insulator sheath can cause the sheath to break down, resulting in more damaged holes and cracks. This causes the mandrel to come into contact with the outside air and rainwater. During the long-term operation, the water diffuses into the inside of the mandrel, and the mandrel is corroded under the long-term action of the acid solution, strong electric field, moist air, etc., the epoxy resin constituting the mandrel is decomposed, and the glass fiber gradually begins to break due to the galvanic reaction. To summarize the whole scenario, the insulator gets crack when the general gravity of the broken glass fiber is not able to reach the comprehensive load force such as the self-weight of the wire and the vibration of the wire.

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